

DATA SUPPLEMENT

Estimating central blood pressure from aortic flow: development and assessment of algorithms

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1. Performance of cBP estimation algorithms

Table S1: Performance of cBP estimation algorithms. Results are presented as mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ) errors between estimated and reference values of $cDBP$, $cMBP$, $cSBP$, and cPP . The RMSE between estimated and reference cBP waves is shown in the last column. Each cBP algorithm was assessed in four datasets and two clinical scenarios: ‘carotid+’ (peripheral BP wave available) and ‘carotid-’ (only peripheral SBP and DBP available).

Dataset	Sce	Algo	Estimation error ($\mu \pm \sigma$) [mmHg]				RMSE
			$cDBP$	$cMBP$	$cSBP$	cPP	
1-D dataset	+	2-Wk	1.2 ± 0.7	0.1 ± 0.1	1.0 ± 0.8	-0.2 ± 1.3	3.4 ± 1.1
		3-Wk	0.1 ± 1.0	0.1 ± 0.1	1.8 ± 1.9	1.7 ± 2.8	2.0 ± 1.7
		1D-Ao	0.1 ± 1.1	0.2 ± 0.6	2.2 ± 1.8	2.1 ± 2.3	2.0 ± 1.0
	-	2-Wk	0.8 ± 1.5	-3.0 ± 1.9	-4.5 ± 5.9	-5.3 ± 7.2	5.0 ± 2.5
		3-Wk	-2.6 ± 0.8	-2.9 ± 1.9	-0.2 ± 4.7	2.4 ± 5.2	5.1 ± 2.0
		1D-Ao	-1.5 ± 1.2	-2.9 ± 1.9	-1.7 ± 5.3	-0.2 ± 6.3	4.2 ± 2.1
Aortic Coarctation	+	2-Wk	0.8 ± 3.1	-3.4 ± 2.8	-15.7 ± 7.2	-16.4 ± 8.5	10.1 ± 3.9
		3-Wk	0.2 ± 2.8	-3.5 ± 2.8	-15.4 ± 7.4	-15.6 ± 8.6	8.0 ± 3.2
		1D-Ao	-3.4 ± 4.8	-2.5 ± 2.6	-0.0 ± 9.7	3.4 ± 10.7	6.4 ± 2.8
	-	2-Wk	-1.5 ± 2.4	-5.5 ± 2.8	-17.3 ± 7.9	-15.8 ± 9.2	10.9 ± 4.3
		3-Wk	-1.8 ± 2.5	-5.7 ± 2.9	-17.2 ± 7.9	-15.4 ± 9.1	8.4 ± 3.6
		1D-Ao	-6.1 ± 2.8	-5.3 ± 3.0	-2.1 ± 9.2	4.1 ± 10.6	7.8 ± 3.3
Normotensive	+	2-Wk	4.7 ± 1.9	0.3 ± 0.1	-8.6 ± 5.0	-13.3 ± 6.2	10.3 ± 3.0
		3-Wk	-4.4 ± 3.5	-0.9 ± 0.7	13.4 ± 13.4	17.9 ± 16.5	8.6 ± 5.5
	-	2-Wk	-0.1 ± 0.5	0.2 ± 2.2	-3.3 ± 3.5	-3.2 ± 3.4	11.0 ± 3.5
		3-Wk	0.2 ± 0.5	-0.2 ± 2.1	-3.7 ± 4.0	-3.9 ± 4.1	5.9 ± 2.4
Hypertensive	+	2-Wk	5.0 ± 3.2	0.3 ± 0.1	-8.3 ± 6.3	-13.3 ± 9.0	10.6 ± 4.1
		3-Wk	-2.9 ± 3.6	-0.9 ± 1.0	8.0 ± 10.6	11.0 ± 13.4	7.1 ± 4.2
	-	2-Wk	-0.3 ± 0.8	-1.1 ± 2.0	-5.5 ± 4.0	-5.2 ± 4.1	11.1 ± 4.2
		3-Wk	0.0 ± 0.6	-1.5 ± 2.0	-6.0 ± 4.7	-6.0 ± 4.9	5.7 ± 2.4

Abbreviations: **Sce**: clinical scenarios (+: ‘carotid+’, -: ‘carotid-’); **Algo**: cBP estimation algorithms (2-Wk: 2-element Windkessel, 3-Wk: 3-element Windkessel, and 1D-Ao: 1-D aortic).

2. Bland-Altman plots assessing cBP estimates

Figure S1: Bland-Altman plots for cBP estimation for 'carotid+'. The 2-element Windkessel (Δ), 3-element Windkessel ($\times$) and 1-D aortic ($\circ$) algorithms were assessed in the 1-D (top), 'Aortic Coarctation' (second row), 'Normotensive' (third row), and 'Hypertensive' (bottom) datasets. y-axes are estimated minus reference cBP values.

Figure S2: Bland-Altman plots for *c*DBP estimation for 'carotid-'. The 2-element Windkessel (Δ), 3-element Windkessel ($\times$) and 1-D aortic ($\circ$) algorithms were assessed in the 1-D (top), 'Aortic Coarctation' (second row), 'Normotensive' (third row), and 'Hypertensive' (bottom) datasets. y-axes are estimated minus reference *c*DBP values.

Figure S3: Bland-Altman plots for cSBP estimation for 'carotid+'. The 2-element Windkessel (Δ), 3-element Windkessel ($\times$) and 1-D aortic ($\circ$) algorithms were assessed in the 1-D (top), 'Aortic Coarctation' (second row), 'Normotensive' (third row), and 'Hypertensive' (bottom) datasets. y-axes are estimated minus reference cSBP values.

Figure S4: Bland-Altman plots for cSBP estimation for ‘carotid-’. The 2-element Windkessel (Δ), 3-element Windkessel ($\times$) and 1-D aortic ($\circ$) algorithms were assessed in the 1-D (top), ‘Aortic Coarctation’ (second row), ‘Normotensive’ (third row), and ‘Hypertensive’ (bottom) datasets. y-axes are estimated minus reference cSBP values.

Figure S5: Bland-Altman plots for *cMBP* estimation for 'carotid+'. The 2-element Windkessel (Δ), 3-element Windkessel ($\times$) and 1-D aortic ($\circ$) algorithms were assessed in the 1-D (top), 'Aortic Coarctation' (second row), 'Normotensive' (third row), and 'Hypertensive' (bottom) datasets. y-axes are estimated minus reference *cMBP* values.

Figure S6: Bland-Altman plots for cMBP estimation for 'carotid-'. The 2-element Windkessel (Δ), 3-element Windkessel ($\times$) and 1-D aortic ($\circ$) algorithms were assessed in the 1-D (top), 'Aortic Coarctation' (second row), 'Normotensive' (third row), and 'Hypertensive' (bottom) datasets. y-axes are estimated minus reference cMBP values.

Figure S7: Bland-Altman plots for *cPP* estimation for 'carotid+'. The 2-element Windkessel (Δ), 3-element Windkessel ($\times$) and '1D-Ao' ($\circ$) algorithms were assessed in the 1-D (top), 'Aortic Coarctation' (second row), 'Normotensive' (third row), and 'Hypertensive' (bottom) datasets. y-axes are estimated minus reference *cPP* values.

cBP algorithms: cPP ('carotid-')

Figure S8: Bland-Altman plots for *cPP* estimation for ‘carotid-’. The 2-element Windkessel (Δ), 3-element Windkessel ($\times$) and ‘1D-Ao’ ($\circ$) algorithms were assessed in the 1-D (top), ‘Aortic Coarctation’ (second row), ‘Normotensive’ (third row), and ‘Hypertensive’ (bottom) datasets. y-axes are estimated minus reference *cPP* values.

3. Reference vs estimated cBP waves

3.1. cBP estimations in a set of randomly chosen 1-D model subjects

Figure S9: cBP wave estimations for ‘carotid+’. cBP waves calculated using the 2-element Windkessel (red lines), 3-element Windkessel (blue lines), and 1-D aortic (black lines) cBP algorithms. They are compared against reference cBP waves from the 1-D model dataset (thick black lines).

Figure S10: cBP wave estimations for ‘carotid-’. cBP waves calculated using the 2-element Windkessel (red lines), 3-element Windkessel (blue lines), and 1-D aortic (black lines) cBP algorithms. They are compared against reference cBP waves from the 1-D model dataset (thick black lines).

3.2. cBP estimations in the 'Aortic Coarctation' dataset

Figure S11: cBP wave estimations for 'carotid+'. cBP waves calculated using the 2-element Windkessel (red lines), 3-element Windkessel (blue lines), and 1-D aortic (black lines) cBP algorithms. They are compared against catheter measurements from the 'Aortic Coarctation' dataset (thick black lines).

Figure S12: cBP wave estimations for 'carotid-'. cBP waves calculated using the 2-element Windkessel (red lines), 3-element Windkessel (blue lines), and 1-D aortic (black lines) cBP algorithms. They are compared against catheter measurements from the 'Aortic Coarctation' dataset (thick black lines).

3.3. cBP estimations in the 'Normotensive' dataset

Figure S13: cBP wave estimations for ‘carotid+’. cBP waves calculated using the 2-element Windkessel (red lines) and 3-element Windkessel (blue lines) cBP algorithms. They are compared against reference cBP waves from the ‘Normotensive’ dataset (thick black lines).

Figure S14: cBP wave estimations for 'carotid-'. cBP waves calculated using the 2-element Windkessel (red lines) and 3-element Windkessel (blue lines) cBP algorithms. They are compared against reference cBP waves from the 'Normotensive' dataset (thick black lines).

3.4. cBP estimations in the 'Hypertensive' dataset

Figure S15: cBP wave estimations for ‘carotid+’. cBP waves calculated using the 2-element Windkessel (red lines) and 3-element Windkessel (blue lines) cBP algorithms. They are compared against reference cBP waves from the ‘Hypertensive’ dataset (thick black lines).

Figure S16: cBP wave estimations for ‘carotid-’. cBP waves calculated using the 2-element Windkessel (red lines) and 3-element Windkessel (blue lines) cBP algorithms. They are compared against reference cBP waves from the ‘Hypertensive’ dataset (thick black lines).